

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN AGRICULTURE: MARKET FORMATION, ECONOMIC IMPACT, AND GLOBAL DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the current state and development trends of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector under conditions of rapid digital transformation of the global economy. It is substantiated that artificial intelligence is becoming one of the key drivers of technological modernization in agriculture, contributing to higher productivity, lower production costs, improved management quality, and more efficient use of natural, labor, and financial resources. The study systematizes the main artificial intelligence technologies used in agriculture, including machine learning, computer vision, big data analytics, robotics, and intelligent decision-support systems, and identifies their economic significance for agricultural production. Particular attention is paid to the formation of the AI market in agriculture through the interaction of demand, supply, investment activity, technological progress, and public policy. The paper analyzes the economic effects of AI implementation, including yield growth, cost optimization, labor productivity improvement, and profitability increase, as well as the major barriers to market expansion, such as high capital intensity, limited access to digital infrastructure, lack of qualified personnel, data representativeness issues, cybersecurity risks, and dependence on technology providers. The global dynamics and regional features of the AI market in agriculture are also considered. It is concluded that artificial intelligence should be viewed not only as an innovative technological tool, but also as a strategic economic resource that shapes new market segments, transforms the agricultural production model, and strengthens the competitiveness and sustainability of the agricultural sector.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; agriculture; AI market; digitalization; global trends.

Statement of the problem. The current stage of development of the global economy is characterised by active digital transformation and widespread introduction of innovative technologies in all areas of economic activity. Artificial intelligence is one of the key technologies that determines the direction of structural changes and production efficiency. In the agricultural sector, its application opens up new opportunities for optimising production processes, increasing productivity, reducing costs and improving management systems. At the same time, the formation of the AI market in the agricultural sector is uneven and is accompanied by a number of economic, technological and institutional constraints. Despite the significant potential of digital technologies, many agricultural producers, especially small and medium-sized farms, face implementation barriers, including high initial investment costs, limited access to digital infrastructure, a shortage of qualified personnel, and insufficient institutional support for innovation. The market for artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector is shaped by the complex interaction of supply, demand, investment activity, government policy, and global economic trends.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In recent years, a significant number of scientific papers have been published on the problems of digitalisation of the agricultural sector, the development of artificial intelligence and its impact on the economic efficiency of agricultural production. Among the scholars who have studied the theoretical, technological and eco-

nomical aspects of artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector, it is worth noting the works of Aghion P., Jones B. F., Jones C. I., Agrawal A., Gans J., Goldfarb A., Brynjolfsson E., Rock D., Syverson C., Elbehri A., Chestnov R., Klerkx L., Jakku E., Labarthe P., Liakos K. G., Busato P., Moshou D., Pearson S., Bochtis D., Mehrabi Z., McDowell M. J., Shang L., Heckelei T., Gerullis M. K., Börner J., Rasch S., Townsend R., Lampietti J., Treguer D., Schroeder K., Haile M., Juergenliemk A., Hasiner E., Horst A., Wolfert S., Verdouw C., Bogaardt M.-J., Vardhan P. N. H., Badavath A., Srivalli P., Rose D. C., Lyon J., de Boon A., Vishnevskiy V. P., Harkushenko O. M.,

Analytical reports and reports of international organisations and institutions, such as the OECD, FAO, World Bank, European Parliamentary Research Service, World Economic Forum, ITU, European Union, as well as materials from international analytical platforms and statistical databases, are also important for the study.

These studies reveal the peculiarities of the digital transformation of agriculture, the role of artificial intelligence in optimising production processes, increasing productivity, developing precision farming, automating management, reducing transaction costs and creating new agribusiness models. The researchers pay special attention to the economic effects of AI solutions, the problems of digital technology diffusion, institutional barriers, accessibility of innovations for small and medium-sized enterprises, and the impact of digitalisation on the competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. However, in scientific research, the issues of its formation, structure and development are often considered in a fragmented manner, focusing mainly on technological aspects or individual applied solutions, without proper economic generalisation. In this regard, there is a need for a comprehensive study of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector, defining its economic nature, structural characteristics, key development factors and current global trends. This is important for the development of effective management decisions both at the level of agricultural business and state policy in the field of economic digitalisation.

The purpose of this article is to study the process of formation of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector, to determine its economic nature, structural characteristics and key development factors, and to assess the impact of AI technologies on the efficiency of agricultural production and current global trends in the development of the agricultural economy.

Explanation of the main points

The current stage of global economic development is characterised by the active implementation of digital technologies in all spheres of public life, which contributes to the formation of new models of management and production processes. Artificial intelligence is one

of the key innovations that determines the directions of transformation of economic systems [1].

The active implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in the agri-food sector is seen as one of the key areas of transformation of modern agriculture. The agricultural industry generates significant amounts of data in the process of production, monitoring of plants, livestock and supply chain management, which creates preconditions for the widespread use of artificial intelligence algorithms to improve the quality of management decisions and automate production processes [2].

In agriculture, artificial intelligence is used as a tool to increase productivity, reduce costs and minimise risks [3; 4]. AI algorithms can reduce resource intensity by 30% and increase yields by 15-20% [5]. To systematise the areas of artificial intelligence use, it is advisable to consider its main technological components (Table 1). The use of these technologies is shaping a new type of agricultural production characterised by a high level of automation, digitalisation and analytical management.

Artificial intelligence can play an important role at all stages of the agri-food chain – from the production of raw materials to their storage, processing, transportation and sale to the end consumer.

Table 1

Main artificial intelligence technologies and their economic importance for the agricultural sector

Technology	Essence	Scope of application	Economic effect
Machine learning	Data analysis and building forecast models	Forecasting yields, prices, risks	Improving the accuracy of management
Computer vision	Image and object recognition	Crop monitoring, disease detection	Reducing crop losses
Big Data analytics	Processing of large data sets	Production planning	Cost optimisation
Robotics	Automated systems	Harvesting, field processing	Reducing labour costs
Intelligent control systems	Decision making based on algorithms	Enterprise management	Increasing productivity

The transformation enabled by artificial intelligence is revolutionising the sustainable development of agriculture, allowing for more efficient use of resources, reduction of waste, and implementation of more environmentally friendly methods [6].

At the current stage of development of the global economy, artificial intelligence is one of the key factors in the transformation of production systems, market structures and mechanisms for the formation of added value [7; 8]. In the agricultural sector, its impact is complex and is manifested not only in the technological improvement of production, but also in the formation of a new economic model of the industry [4; 9]. Artificial intelligence is gradually turning into a strategic resource that ensures an increase in the efficiency of the use of production factors, a change in the cost structure,

productivity growth and the formation of new competitive advantages. The use of artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector contributes to the transition to more sustainable development models focused on the efficient use of natural resources and reducing the negative impact on the environment

Integration of AI into production processes changes the cost structure and reduces information asymmetry, which has a positive impact on the efficiency of management decision-making [7]. Analytical systems allow for more accurate forecasting of yields, optimisation of crop structure, and minimisation of risks associated with weather or price fluctuations (10; 11).

At the same time, the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies is accompanied by a number of economic and organisational challenges (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Challenges for the introduction of AI in agriculture *Built by the authors on the basis of [12-14].

The risks of implementing AI in the agricultural sector include dependence on technology suppliers, possible system failures, cyber threats, and ethical issues [12].

For agricultural AI, the representativeness of data on crops, soils, and climatic zones is critical [13]. A significant obstacle to the widespread adoption of AI solutions in agriculture is the high capital intensity of modern technologies. Around 80% of farms in the world are small, and they often lack sufficient financial resources or access to traditional lending. [15]. Thus, despite the significant potential of artificial intelligence to increase the efficiency of agricultural production, its implementation is associated with a set of economic, technological and social challenges.

The AI market in the agricultural sector is being formed at the intersection of three waves: (1) smart farming and digitalisation of production (sensors, satellite data, IoT, digital platforms), (2) automation and robotisation (autonomous vehicles, robotic operations),

(3) intensive development of machine learning methods and, in particular, deep learning for diagnostics and forecasting [3]. Segmentation of demand for agricultural AI in the literature corresponds to decision-making points in the production and sales cycle: crop planning, input, harvesting, logistics, access to finance and insurance [16]. It should be noted that the agricultural AI market is not identical to the software market. It depends on assets (communication, power supply, geospatial data, service network, human resources) and institutions (data rules, trust, standards) [17].

The development of the AI market in the agricultural sector is a complex multifactorial process that depends on the level of digitalisation of the economy, investment activity, scientific and technological potential, and government support for innovation. The structure of the agricultural AI market is shown in Fig. 2

Figure 2. Structure of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector *Built by the authors on the basis of [3; 7; 16-18]

From the economic point of view, the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies contributes to the formation of new market segments, the emergence of innovative products and services, as well as changes in the structure of demand for agricultural technologies.

The economic modelling of the impact of AI on agricultural production and the formation of the market for agricultural innovations in the literature is reduced to two interrelated tasks:

1) the impact model, i.e. how information and automation translate into productivity and economic results. In this logic, AI acts as an information capital that reduces information asymmetry, transaction costs, and decision errors [19].

2) the market diffusion model, i.e. how fast and in which segments the implementation takes place, and how it is reflected in market indicators (sales, investments, and the growth of the number of transactions) [20].

The impact of artificial intelligence on agricultural production should be viewed through the prism of economic models of technological development and endogenous growth, in which knowledge and technology are internal drivers of productivity [21]. In the digital economy, the traditional factors (labour, capital, natural resources) are supplemented by information technology capital, which includes data, software solutions, algorithms, and analytical platforms [22]. Artificial intelligence forms the core of a new production factor, ensuring an increase in the marginal productivity of traditional resources [8]. The economic model of the impact of artificial intelligence on the agricultural sector can be presented as a system of interaction between three key blocks: resource, technological and performance [3; 9]. Within the resource block, an information base is formed that includes data on soils, climatic conditions, crop conditions, use of machinery, and market parameters. The technology block includes analytical systems, machine learning algorithms, digital platforms and intelligent decision support systems. The resultant block reflects the economic impact of using artificial intelligence, including increased yields, reduced costs, increased labour productivity, and increased profitability [10; 23].

AI is a tool for optimising the production function of an agricultural enterprise. While the traditional production function depended on the ratio of labour, capital and natural resources, the modern model involves the integration of digital technologies that increase the efficiency of each of these factors. In modern studies,

digitalisation is seen as a systemic factor in the transformation of the production function and the structure of economic growth, which forms a new model of value creation based on data and digital capital [24].

The impact of artificial intelligence on the agricultural sector is also manifested in the formation of a new risk management model. The high volatility of global agricultural markets creates a demand for analytical forecasting systems, including artificial intelligence tools that reduce information asymmetry and increase the accuracy of management decisions [10; 25]. This increases the sustainability of agricultural enterprises and reduces their vulnerability to external shocks.

From the perspective of market conditions theory, artificial intelligence is a factor in the structural transformation of the agricultural market. Its introduction changes the nature of demand for technological products, forms new economic relations between producers and technology suppliers, and creates preconditions for the emergence of new business models [23]. Automation and robotisation of production are changing the structure of employment, creating demand for specialists in data analysis, digital management and innovation management.

Thus, the formation of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector should be viewed through the prism of an economic model that reflects the interaction of supply, demand, and external macroeconomic factors (Fig. 3). The market development is driven by global drivers, including growing demand for food, increased investment in digital technologies, government support for innovation, and technological progress. Supply in the market is generated by IT companies, technology start-ups, software developers and digital platform manufacturers. Demand is generated by agricultural enterprises, farms, and government agencies that are interested in improving production efficiency and reducing costs. The interaction of these two components shapes the current market environment, which manifests itself in changes in the price level of technological solutions, investment volumes, the degree of competition and market growth rates. An important feature of this model is its dynamic nature. The artificial intelligence market environment is changing under the influence of technological innovations, financial flows, government policy, and global economic trends. The economic results of the market's functioning are manifested in increased agricultural productivity, increased profitability of enterprises and the formation of new business models.

Figure 3. Model of market formation of artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector *proposed by the authors

Thus, artificial intelligence is not only a technological tool, but also an important economic resource that defines new directions for the development of the agricultural sector, shapes the current market environment and ensures increased production efficiency.

Globally, the market for artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector is showing steady growth, driven by rising demand for food, the need for efficient use of natural resources, climate challenges, and the need to optimise agricultural production. Technologies for precision farming, yield forecasting, and automated monitoring of soil and crop conditions are shaping a new economic environment in the agricultural market, where digital innovations are becoming a key factor in

competitiveness. According to the World Bank, in 2023, the global market for artificial intelligence technologies in the agricultural sector was estimated at around USD 1.5 billion. By 2032, it is expected to grow to about USD 10.2 billion, which corresponds to an average annual growth rate of about 5.5 per cent. This corresponds to an average annual growth rate of about 24-25%. [11]. According to Global Market Insights, the global AI market in the agricultural sector was estimated at about USD 4.7 billion in 2024. [26].

The structure of the global market for artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector by main areas of application is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Structure of the AI market in the agricultural sector by application, 2025 [27]

The largest market share is occupied by precision farming technologies, as they provide the most direct economic benefit to agricultural enterprises by increasing yields, optimising resource use, and reducing costs. At the same time, soil, crop and livestock monitoring systems, which generate large amounts of data for further analysis, account for a significant share.

Hardware systems for precision farming, including sensors, navigation systems, automated machinery control systems, and equipment for monitoring agricultural production, play an important role in the development of the smart technologies market. The dynamics of this segment is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Market share of hardware systems for precision agriculture in the world in 2018 and 2025, by type [28]

An analysis of the dynamics of the development of hardware systems for precision farming shows a gradual expansion of their use in the agricultural sector. This is due to the growing need to automate production processes, improve the accuracy of agro-technological operations, and optimise resource use. Service robotics is a separate area of smart agricultural production development. Modern robotic systems are used to automate certain production processes, such as harvesting, sorting, crop monitoring and machinery management

[29]. The growth of this market segment indicates the gradual transition of agricultural production to a new technological model based on the widespread use of automated systems and robotic systems.

The level of adoption of digital technologies in agriculture varies significantly between regions of the world. The share of farmers who are already using or planning to introduce new technologies is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Share of farmers using or planning to adopt at least one new technology globally in 2022 and 2024, by region [30]

As of 2024, more than half of farmers worldwide were ready or had already adopted at least one new agricultural technology on their farms. Regional analysis shows that the highest level of adoption of innovative

agricultural technologies is observed in North America, Europe and Latin America. This is due to a more developed digital infrastructure, access to investment, and a

high level of technological modernisation in the agricultural sector.

The main characteristics of the development of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector by region are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Regional structure of the global AI market in the agricultural sector		
Region	Development characteristics	Key drivers
North America	The most mature market	High investment, automation, digital farming
Europe	Stable technological growth	Environmental standards, precision farming
Asia Pacific	The fastest growth	Government programmes, digitalisation, mobile AI solutions
Latin America	Emerging market	Agroholdings, export crops
Middle East and Africa	Initial stage	Water shortage, smart irrigation

An analysis of the regional market structure shows that the development of artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector depends not only on the technological level of economic development, but also on institutional support for innovation, the availability of investment, and the specifics of agricultural production.

Taking into account the results of the study, it is advisable to formulate a number of scientifically based proposals to improve the efficiency of the development of the artificial intelligence market in the agricultural sector. First of all, it is important to formulate a comprehensive state policy aimed at stimulating the digitalisation of agricultural production, in particular by developing digital infrastructure in rural areas, supporting the introduction of innovative technologies and creating a favourable institutional environment for the functioning of agricultural innovation ecosystems. An important area is to intensify investment activity in the field of agricultural AI, which involves expanding access to financial resources for agricultural enterprises to implement modern technological solutions, as well as developing partnerships between agribusiness, IT companies, and startups. This will help accelerate the diffusion of innovations and the formation of new business models in the agricultural sector. Special attention should be paid to improving the institutional environment for the AI market, in particular in terms of regulating data circulation, ensuring its security, and building trust in digital technologies. It is also important to develop standards for the use of AI in the agricultural sector, which will help increase the transparency and efficiency of market relations.

Conclusions and suggestions

In summary, artificial intelligence is an important factor in the economic development of the agricultural sector, ensuring technological modernisation of production and creating new markets for innovative solutions. Its widespread use contributes to the transition to smart agriculture based on data, automation and digital management. The global market for artificial intelligence in the agricultural sector is characterised by high growth rates, active implementation of innovative technologies and expansion of the application areas of intelligent systems. The main drivers of this market are the digitalisation of agricultural production, increased investment in technological solutions, and the growing need for efficient resource management. In the future,

the role of artificial intelligence will only grow, and its development will be determined by the level of integration of digital solutions into production processes, the intensity of investment, and the speed of adaptation of agricultural enterprises to new technological conditions.

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